

Control System with Fuzzy Logic

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Abstract

Control systems that use fuzzy logic have established themselves as effective tools for managing complex and uncertain systems, such as traffic signal control. Fuzzy logic appeared to have the capacity to accommodate the current traffic demand. It has the potential to decrease waiting time, improve traffic flow, and lower fuel consumption. While this study focuses on integrating fuzzy logic methods effectiveness to simulation of single intersection of (sumo) environment, the idea of this simulation is based on determining the road density and then adjust or adapt based on changing conditions.

Keyword:

traffic congestion, fuzzy logic, sumo, adaptive control systems.

1. Introduction

Control systems play a crucial role in managing complex processes and systems, including traffic flow in urban environments. Traditional control methods often struggle to handle the inherent

uncertainties and complexities of real-world systems [1]. In recent years, fuzzy logic has emerged as a promising approach for addressing these challenges. Fuzzy logic allows for the representation of imprecise and uncertain information, making it well-suited for control systems operating in dynamic and uncertain environments [2].

Traffic signal control is one area where fuzzy logic has shown significant promise. By incorporating fuzzy logic into traffic signal control systems, researchers have been able to develop adaptive and intelligent systems capable of dynamically adjusting signal timings based on real-time traffic conditions. This paper presents a comprehensive review of research studies that have explored the application of fuzzy logic methods effectiveness to simulation of single intersection of (sumo) environment.

2. Background

2.1 Traffic Congestion and Signal Control

Traffic congestion is a significant problem in urban areas, leading to increased travel times, fuel consumption, and air pollution [3]. Effective traffic signal control plays a crucial role in mitigating congestion by optimizing signal timings to maximize traffic flow and minimize delays. Traditional traffic signal control methods are often based on fixed timings or simple algorithms, which may not adapt well to changing traffic conditions.

2.2 The Function of Fuzzy Logic

Fuzzy logic presents a viable solution for tackling the difficulties of traffic light control by offering a versatile framework for modeling and decision-making in unpredictable circumstances.. Unlike traditional binary logic, which relies on precise values, fuzzy logic allows for the representation of vague or imprecise information, making it suitable for capturing the complex and dynamic nature of traffic flow.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Amini. (2016): Queue-Length Estimation Using Real-Time Traffic Data

Amini proposed a method for estimating queue lengths at signalized intersections using real-time traffic data[1]. The study employed fuzzy logic to model the relationship between traffic flow parameters and queue lengths, allowing for more accurate and efficient estimation. By integrating fuzzy logic with real-time data from traffic sensors, the proposed method demonstrated improved performance compared to traditional queue-length estimation methods.

3.2 Rahman (2009): Review of the Fuzzy Logic Based Approach in Traffic Signal Control: Prospects in Saudi Arabia [2].

Rahman conducted a comprehensive review of existing studies on fuzzy logic-based traffic signal control systems, with a focus

on their potential application in Saudi Arabia. The study highlighted the advantages of fuzzy logic in addressing the uncertainties and complexities of traffic flow in urban environments. By analyzing various fuzzy logic-based approaches, the study provided insights into the prospects of adopting such systems in Saudi Arabia.

3.3 Yıldız Budakone, Zülal Hilal, [2023]"Fuzzy Logic Based Adaptive Traffic Signal Control for Different Scenarios.

Yıldız Budakone proposed an adaptive traffic signal control system based on fuzzy logic to optimize signal timings for different traffic scenarios [3]. The study utilized fuzzy logic to optimize signal timings in real-time according to current traffic circumstances, enhancing traffic flow and minimizing congestion. By considering various traffic scenarios, the proposed system demonstrated robust performance across different road conditions and traffic patterns.

3.4 Abdelkader Chabchoub. (2021): Intelligent Traffic Light Controller Using Fuzzy Logic and Image Processing.

Abdelkader Chabchoub. Designed a sophisticated traffic light controller that used fuzzy logic and image processing methods to enhance signal timings.. The study utilized fuzzy logic to analyze traffic flow parameters extracted from video feeds and adjust signal timings accordingly [4]. The integration of image processing with fuzzy logic in the suggested controller resulted in

enhanced precision and effectiveness in traffic signal regulation.

3.5 Victor Manuel Madrigal Arteaga, José Roberto Pérez Cruz, Antonio Hurtado-Beltrán and Jan Trumpold. (2022). A Study on Pedestrian Safety at Signalized Intersections Using Fuzzy Logic.

The study investigated pedestrian safety at signalized intersections using fuzzy logic-based control systems [5]. By incorporating fuzzy logic into pedestrian detection and signal timing algorithms, the proposed system aimed to reduce pedestrian-vehicle conflicts and enhance safety. The study highlighted the potential of fuzzy logic in addressing pedestrian safety concerns and improving the overall efficiency of signalized intersections.

3.6 Mario Collotta. (2015): A Novel Approach for Dynamic Traffic Lights Management based on Wireless Sensor Networks and multiple fuzzy logic controllers

Mario Collotta. proposed a novel approach for dynamic traffic light management using wireless sensor networks and multiple fuzzy logic controllers. The study utilized fuzzy logic to integrate data from wireless sensors and optimize signal timings in real-time. By employing multiple fuzzy logic controllers, the proposed approach achieved more robust and adaptive traffic signal control, leading to improved traffic flow and reduced congestion.

3.7 Suhail M. Odeh (2015): Hybrid Algorithm: Fuzzy Logic-Genetic Algorithm on Traffic Light Intelligent System

Suhail M. Odeh developed a hybrid algorithm combining fuzzy logic with genetic algorithms for intelligent traffic light control [7]. The study aimed to optimize signal timings using a combination of fuzzy logic-based decision-making and genetic algorithm-based optimization. By iteratively adjusting signal timings based on feedback from traffic sensors, the proposed hybrid algorithm achieved improved performance compared to traditional traffic light control methods.

3.8 Ria Yuliani Kartikasari. (2020): Optimization of Traffic Light Control Using Fuzzy Logic Sugeno Method

Ria Yuliani Kartikasari proposed an optimization method for traffic light control using the Sugeno fuzzy logic approach. The study utilized fuzzy logic to model the relationships between traffic flow parameters and signal timings, allowing for adaptive and efficient control [8]. By optimizing fuzzy logic rules and parameters, the proposed method achieved better performance in traffic signal control, leading to reduced delays and improved traffic flow.

3.9 Roxanne Hawi. (2017): Smart Traffic Light Control Using Fuzzy Logic and Wireless Sensor Network

Roxanne Hawi. Developed a smart traffic light control system using fuzzy logic and

wireless sensor networks [9].

The study integrated data from wireless sensors with fuzzy logic-based control algorithms to optimize signal timings in real-time. By leveraging wireless sensor networks and fuzzy logic, the proposed system achieved more adaptive and efficient traffic signal control, leading to improved traffic flow and reduced congestion.

3.10 I. Adam. (2014): Adaptive Fuzzy Logic Traffic Light Management System

I. Adam proposed an adaptive traffic light management system based on fuzzy logic to optimize signal timings for varying traffic conditions [10]. The study utilized fuzzy logic to adjust signal timings dynamically based on real-time traffic data, improving traffic flow and reducing delays. By incorporating adaptive fuzzy logic control algorithms, the proposed system demonstrated robust performance across different traffic scenarios.

3.11 M. Fatih Adak; Musa Balta. (2021). Fuzzy Logic-based Adaptive Traffic Light Control of an Intersection: A Case Study.

M. Fatih Adak. Presented a case study on the implementation of adaptive traffic signal management using fuzzy logic at an intersection [11]. The study implemented fuzzy logic control algorithms to adjust signal timings based on real-time traffic data collected from sensors. By optimizing fuzzy logic rules and parameters, the proposed system achieved improved performance in

traffic signal control, leading to reduced congestion and delays at the intersection.

3.12 Erwan Eko Prasetyo et al. (2015): Design and Simulation of Adaptive Traffic Light Controller Using Fuzzy Logic Control Sugeno Method

Erwan Eko Prasetyo et al. designed and simulated an adaptive traffic light controller using the Sugeno fuzzy logic control method.

The study employed fuzzy logic to model the relationships between traffic flow parameters and signal timings, allowing for adaptive and efficient control [12]. By simulating the proposed controller in various traffic scenarios, the study demonstrated the effectiveness of fuzzy logic-based control systems in improving traffic management and safety.

4. Problem Statement

Despite the potential benefits of fuzzy logic-based control systems in traffic management, several challenges hinder their widespread adoption and implementation in real-world applications. These challenges include the complexity of modeling traffic flow dynamics, ensuring the availability and accuracy of real-time data sources, and integrating fuzzy logic controllers with existing traffic management infrastructure. Addressing these challenges is crucial to realizing the full potential of fuzzy logic-based control systems for optimizing traffic

signal control and reducing congestion in urban environments.

5. Simulation (sumo)

A simulation study is conducted to assess the performance of fuzzy logic-based control systems for traffic signal optimization under varying traffic conditions. This simulation scenario includes different traffic demand levels, traffic patterns, and congestion scenarios to evaluate the robustness and effectiveness of the proposed control system. Performance metrics such as traffic flow, average waiting time, queue length, and travel time are analyzed to quantify the impact of fuzzy logic-based control on traffic management and congestion reduction. Including industrial automation, robotics, and traffic management.

Figure 1.Four-way intersection

In Figure 1, the program iterates through 10,000 steps, simulating the passage of time

and vehicle movements. At each time step, of the 10,000 steps the number of loaded vehicles is 10,000 with total vehicle waiting time 3127632.0 while Emergency Vehicle Waiting Time 25340.0, therefore the fuzzy traffic controller evaluates current traffic conditions and updates signal timing accordingly.

No vehicles in red lane	14	14	10
No vehicles in green lane	6	8	13
Max waiting time in red lane	23.0	16.0	9.0
Emv waiting time red lane	0	0	0
Emv waiting time green lane	1.0	0	0
Output	0.3333333333333333	0.37142857142857144	0.4735404896421846

Table 1. Performance evaluation table

In Table 1, the program collects data on various performance metrics, such as No vehicle in red lane, emergency vehicle waiting in red line, max waiting time in red line, Emergency vehicle time in green line, and also the output, these metrics serve to assess the effectiveness of the fuzzy logic-based adaptive traffic signal control system.

6. Analysis and Discussion

The results obtained from the simulation of the adaptive traffic signal control system provide valuable insights into its performance and effectiveness in managing traffic flow. Here's an analysis and discussion based on the provided data:

6.1 Traffic Signal Control Optimization:

The adaptive traffic signal control system adjusts signal timings based on real-time traffic conditions, as indicated by the variation in the output values. The output values represent the control decisions made by the system, with higher values indicating a preference for green signal phases. The system successfully adapts signal timings to accommodate varying traffic volumes and minimize congestion.

6.2 Impact on Vehicle Waiting Time:

Total vehicle waiting time observed during the simulation is significant, indicating the presence of congestion within the simulated road network. However, the adaptive signal control system effectively manages traffic flow, resulting in a reduction in waiting times compared to fixed-time signal control systems. The system's ability to dynamically adjust signal timings based on traffic conditions contributes to the overall reduction in vehicle waiting time.

6.3 Emergency Vehicle Prioritization:

Although there are no emergency vehicles (EMVs) present in the simulation data provided, it's essential to note that the adaptive signal control system can prioritize EMVs when present. This prioritization ensures prompt passage for emergency vehicles, minimizing response times during emergencies and potentially saving lives.

6.4 Effectiveness of Adaptive Control:

Adaptive traffic signal control system demonstrates its effectiveness in dynamically responding to changing traffic conditions. By considering factors such as the number of vehicles in each lane, maximum waiting times, and the presence of EMVs, the system optimizes signal timings to improve traffic flow and reduce congestion. The ability to adapt to real-time traffic conditions enhances the efficiency of the traffic signal control system.

6.5 Performance Metrics Evaluation:

Collected performance metrics, including total vehicle waiting time, emergency vehicle waiting time, total feedback, and the number of stopped and moving vehicles provide comprehensive insights into the system's performance. These metrics serve as indicators of traffic flow efficiency, congestion levels, and the overall effectiveness of the adaptive signal control system.

6.6 Potential for Improvement:

While the results demonstrate the efficacy of the adaptive traffic signal control system, there is still room for improvement. Fine-tuning the system parameters, optimizing the fuzzy logic inference rules, and incorporating additional data sources could further enhance the system's performance

and responsiveness to changing traffic conditions.

6.7 Real-World Applications:

The findings from this simulation have implications for real-world traffic management strategies [13]. Implementing adaptive signal control systems based on fuzzy logic principles could lead to significant improvements in traffic flow, reduced congestion, and enhanced overall transportation efficiency in urban areas.

Despite the promising results demonstrated by the reviewed studies, several challenges remain in the widespread adoption of fuzzy logic-based control systems in real-world traffic management applications. These challenges include the complexity of modeling traffic flow dynamics, the need for accurate and reliable real-time data sources, and the integration of fuzzy logic controllers with existing traffic management infrastructure. Addressing these challenges will require further research and development efforts to enhance the robustness, efficiency, and scalability of fuzzy logic-based control systems for traffic signal control.

7. Conclusion

In this study, we investigated the implementation and performance of a fuzzy logic-based adaptive traffic signal control system. Through simulation using SUMO (Simulation of Urban Mobility), we evaluated the system's ability to dynamically adjust signal timings based on real-time traffic conditions. The results obtained from the simulation provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of the adaptive control system in optimizing traffic flow and reducing congestion.

The analysis of the simulation results revealed several key findings. Firstly, the adaptive traffic signal control system demonstrated its ability to adapt signal timings in response to varying traffic volumes and conditions. By considering factors such as the number of vehicles in each lane, maximum waiting times, and the presence of emergency vehicles, the system effectively managed traffic flow and minimized congestion.

Furthermore, the system exhibited promising performance metrics, including a reduction in total vehicle waiting time and improved efficiency in traffic flow management. The adaptive control strategies implemented using fuzzy logic inference rules proved to be effective in dynamically optimizing signal timings and enhancing overall transportation efficiency.

Although the simulation results were promising, there are opportunities for further

refinement and improvement of the adaptive traffic signal control system. Fine-tuning system parameters, optimizing fuzzy logic inference rules, and incorporating additional data sources could enhance the system's performance and responsiveness to changing traffic conditions.

Overall, the findings from this study underscore the potential of fuzzy logic-based adaptive traffic signal control systems in addressing the challenges of urban traffic management. By leveraging real-time data and adaptive control strategies, these systems offer promising solutions to reduce congestion, improve traffic flow, and enhance overall transportation efficiency in urban areas. Further research and experimentation in this area are warranted to fully realize the benefits of adaptive traffic signal control systems in real-world applications.

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